

Evaluating Energy-Efficient Design Strategies in Residential Buildings: A Case Study of Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract: The rising demand for energy in Nigeria's residential sector, mostly caused by poor power supply and increase in energy costs, highlights the need for energy-efficient and sustainable architecture. This study investigated the barriers and implementation of energy-efficient architectural design strategies in residential buildings across 3 main urban areas in Owerri (Municipal, North, and West). The aim is to evaluate how effective these strategies are in reducing high energy consumption and improving thermal comfort. A mixed-method approach involving questionnaires, existing building assessments, and interviews with professionals and homeowners was adopted and a total of Twenty seven buildings (nine from each zone) evaluated. The research evaluated design elements like ventilation, building orientation, roofing materials, insulation, and the adoption of renewable energy sources. Data were collected through interviews with occupants and resident architects. The results show that some passive cooling strategies like natural cross-ventilation, light-colored roofing, use of locally-sourced insulating materials, and shaded openings, were modestly applied (in about 75% of buildings). This significantly minimized indoor temperatures thereby reducing too much reliance on artificial cooling systems. However, other important features like optimal building orientation, solar integration, and roof insulation are still underutilized. The study concluded that there is a gap in the merging of principles of effective design between developers and builders in these areas. This gap may be as a result of lack of awareness, financial incapability, and weak implementation of already existing building energy codes. It therefore recommended an approach to include public awareness campaigns, building code revisions, policy incentives, and well-structured architectural education.

Keywords: *Energy efficiency, Sustainable architecture, Passive design, Residential buildings, Design strategies*

Introduction

The built environment occupies a very large portion of energy consumption globally, with residential buildings solely generating a substantial amount of greenhouse gas emissions and skyrocketing energy demands. In developing countries such as Nigeria, where the supply of power is barely constant, and energy cost is high, the need for building designs which are energy-efficient has become very critical. Energy efficiency in architecture centers on minimizing energy consumption by the use of effective passive design strategies like shading, insulation, daylighting, natural ventilation, and thermal mass which can reduce energy demand significantly and enhance indoor comfort (Ajayi et al., 2023) . Complementing these passive design strategies, the integration of renewable energy elements such as rooftop solar photovoltaic (PV) systems can reduce both operational carbon emissions and energy use in residential buildings (Nwaji et al., 2024)

Owerri, the capital city of Imo State, located in the southeastern part of Nigeria, experiences a tropical climate characterized by high temperatures and humidity. However, most residential buildings in that region are still built with conventional building designs which ignore climatic responsiveness. Due to

this, occupants tend to rely mostly on mechanical cooling systems. This contributes to higher energy consumption and increases cost which may become burdensome. Policy enforcement, technical expertise, and lack of awareness, in energy-efficient practices have further worsened the situation. A study of the present state of energy-efficiency strategies in residential buildings using a net-zero-energy prototype in Owerri showed that re-orienting the building north-south, using bricks in place of concrete blocks, and reducing east-west glazing minimized cooling burdens by almost 19.3% and reduced the cost of energy by 11%. However, these strategies are still underutilized. In some regions in Nigeria, the performance of passive design has also been validated. For example, in Kaduna, a tropical savanna zone, field experiments carried out on bungalows with the use of reflective external finishes, rooftop insulation, and controlled mechanical ventilation, showed that the indoor thermal stability was improved and energy reliance reduced (Xi et al., 2025). Additionally, wall systems with ventilated cavity which were accessed in recent studies achieved great reductions in indoor temperature with up to 5 °C through aeration of passive facade, showing the capabilities of facade design's thermal control (Open Journal of Environmental Research, 2024).

Also, in Calabar, a research highlighted how architectural designs invoking local layouts of courtyards and buoyancy-driven airflow (the authors named it “breathing building”), can generate effective passive cooling entirely in multipurpose structures (Okonkwo et al., 2022) . Systematic studies across the area further emphasized the efficiency of passive and biophilic solutions, integrating ventilation-driven layouts, greenery, thermal mass, and shading devices in enhancing occupant comfort and energy performance and in tropical residential structures (Dimuna et al., 2025; Ezeoke & Chike, 2023). This study examined the present status of energy-efficient design strategies in residential buildings in Owerri, Imo State, and drawing attention to both active and passive techniques. It evaluated how extensively climate-responsive design is being used and also identifies barriers and gaps (like low awareness, limited technical expertise, weak policy enforcement, others). By analyzing the dominant building practices in Owerri and referencing on peer-reviewed insights from similar contexts, the study aim proposed cost-effective recommendations which will practically improve sustainable housing development. By so doing, it contributes to a more elaborate discourse concerning climate-responsive architecture and aligns with

federal government objectives on environmental sustainability, energy conservation, and reduced GHG emissions.

Materials and Methods

The case study approach of this study adopted a mixed-method; in that it combined both quantitative and qualitative method of data collection procedures in assessing most practices of energy-efficiency in residential buildings in Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. The research centered on three urban areas: Owerri Municipal, Owerri North, and Owerri west, selected because of their varied population densities and architectural patterns.

Data Collection

Primary data were gathered through:

Well-structured questionnaires which were given to available residents, builders, and a few architects (a total number of 45 questionnaires: 15 for each zone).

Building assessments made on-site at 27 residential buildings (9 per zone) to evaluate active and passive energy-efficiency features.

Semi-structured interviews with 3 major personnel, an architect, a town planner and a

surveyor from Imo State Ministry of Lands and Housing.

Secondary data sources included:

Existing (published) literature.

Nigerian Building Codes (2006)

National Building Energy Efficiency Code (NBEEC, 2017)

Architectural drawings (including master plan), and building regulations in the state.

Data Analysis

Analysis of Quantitative data from questionnaires were conducted using SPSS (version 20) for descriptive statistics (standard deviation, frequency, mean), while the analysis of qualitative data from interviews were conducted using thematic content analysis.

A checklist of energy-efficient features was utilized during site visits, centering on:

Building orientation

Roof insulation and material types

Use of renewable energy (e.g., solar panels)

Natural ventilation strategies

Window-to-wall ratio

Shading device

Ethical Considerations

Participants were notified of the purpose of the study, and informed consent was received. Personalities were kept anonymous and all data were used strictly for study purposes.

Results and Discussion

General Awareness of Energy Efficiency

The questionnaire revealed that only 40% of respondents were fully aware of energy-efficient design principles. An additional 35% had partial knowledge, while 25% were completely unaware (see figure 2). Awareness levels were higher among homeowners in Owerri municipal compared to Owerri north and Owerri west, possibly due to greater exposure to modern housing developments.

Figure 1 Checklist of Energy-Efficient features frequency of use in inspected Buildings

Figure 2 Awareness of Passive Design Strategies among Respondents

Prevalence of Energy-Efficient Features

Site assessments of twenty seven buildings showed poor passive design strategies integration. The prevalent existing feature was cross-ventilation (found in 75% of buildings),

mostly in older houses with open-plan layouts and wider openings. However, 10% of buildings had no form of roof insulation, while 15% depended on solar panels, predominantly in high-income neighborhoods within the three areas.

Table 1 Frequency of Energy-Efficient Features in Surveyed Buildings.

Feature	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Remarks
Cross ventilation	5	75	Mostly available in traditional compounds
Roof insulation	2	10	Primarily found in modern facilities
Solar Panels	3	10	Has a high cost installation rate
Shading devices (trees, roof overhangs)	4	72	Integrated into landscaping
Light coloured roofs/walls	2	19	Designed on demand

Orientation and Use of Material

Building materials like blocks, cement, and aluminum roofing sheets is widely used in construction across all three cities. However, only a few buildings met the requirements in optimizing wind direction and natural lighting. Only 8 out of the 27 homes had favorable orientation (east to west), while others were dictated by the shape of the plot or land constraints.

Constraints and Preferences of Residents

Respondents said that high cost, lack of technical knowledge and guidance remains the major hindrance to embracing energy-efficient designs. Many went for air conditioning against passive methods in a bid

to achieve immediate comfort, even if it is more expensive.

This study finding reveals an obvious gap between energy-efficient design principles and the prevalent practices in residential buildings in Owerri, Imo State. In spite of the growing awareness of global sustainability issues, many homes within the study area still depend on conventional design methods which have poor adaptation to local climate. This observation is in line with the conclusions of Ezeanya (2018), who stated that energy-conscious architecture in Nigeria is still majorly theoretical and practically underutilized.

The relatively high availability of cross-ventilation (75%) among analyzed buildings suggests a certain level of consideration regarding passive cooling, especially in older buildings. This shows that traditional architectural touches like wide windows and open courtyards, still plays a major role in maintaining indoor comfort. However, some passive techniques such as shading and roof insulation were occasionally implemented, confirming the claim by Adebayo (2015) that modern housing in Nigeria often sacrifices climate responsiveness for aesthetics and compactness.

The renewable energy technologies (especially solar panels), which is on a low adoption, is another major finding. With only 15% of buildings putting solar power to use, the potential for decentralized generation of energy remains widely untapped. Cost was cited as the major barrier, consistent with Olotuah and Adesiji (2014), who debated that high cost of installation affect middle and low income homeowners in Nigeria and deter them from investing in clean energy.

Another design tool which is underutilized is Orientation. With only 8 out of 27 buildings in proper alignment along the east-west axis, it is obvious that plot shape and land constraints, sometimes developer preferences,

often overshadow environmental considerations. This indicates lack of proper urban planning enforcement and architectural oversight.

Furthermore, the widespread use of aluminum roofing sheets and concrete blocks (which is widely available and cost-effective), provides limited amount of insulation against the region's high temperature. These materials absorb and retain heat, increasing indoor temperatures thereby leading to excessive use of air conditioners and fans.

The results highlight a pressing need for design education (context-specific), energy-efficiency guidelines with high accessibility, and policy support based on sustainable architecture as lack of these will expose residential development in Owerri Imo State to continuous dependency on energy reinforcement and environmental stress.

This study emphasizes on the importance of incorporating design strategies which are climate-responsive into both retrofitting efforts and new constructions. Imo State architects can work on improving building performance in the state by bridging traditional design logic with modern energy practices in order to promote environmental sustainability.

Although this research gives valuable insights in applying energy-efficient strategies in Imo State, most of the limiting factors should be put into consideration. Firstly, the study sample size was limited to 27 residential buildings and 45 respondents across the three zones. Inasmuch as this scope is sufficient for exploratory analysis, it may not fully capture the diverse practices of buildings across the entire study area, especially in its suburban/rural regions where construction practices may slightly differ.

Secondly, the study depended mostly on self-reported data via interviews and questionnaires, which may be as a result of inaccuracies or bias in respondents perceptions and knowledge. Although efforts were made to ensure accurate information via on-site assessments, there can still be gaps in accuracy of some responses.

Also, the study centered mostly on design and architectural elements and never conducted technical measurements of indoor thermal comfort or energy consumption levels by the use of energy meters or sensors. Future research which can incorporate data for real-time energy performance would provide a more comprehensive understanding concerning energy efficiency in buildings.

Also, due to lack of proper awareness among most homeowners, some respondents were totally unable to give the needed information on energy-efficiency.

Finally, during the building assessment, there were restrictions to some buildings. Also, time constraints limited field observations duration. Despite the encountered limitations, the findings provide a basic understanding of prevalent practices and serve as a foundation for policy advocacy and further research in the area of sustainable housing development.

Conclusion

This study assessed the factors militating energy-efficient design strategies in residential buildings in Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria, its awareness level, and adoption. The study was carried out through assessments of existing buildings, field surveys, and interviews across three major zones: Owerri Municipal, Owerri North, and Owerri West. It was evident that the overall integration of energy efficient design principles into some passive design strategies like informal shading and cross ventilation was limited even though they exist. The findings reveal an alarming rate of dependence on conventional building

materials and layouts which neglect the tropical climate of Owerri. This has resulted to an increase in reliance on artificial cooling systems, thereby increasing household costs and energy demand. Furthermore, this study points to the fact that many residential developments lack deliberate plan for insulation, solar orientation, or renewable energy systems. These gaps are mostly as a result of three major factors: (1) little or no awareness among homeowners and professionals, (2) cost implications of technologies and sustainable materials, and (3) poor enforcement of energy efficiency policies. This reflects broader issues witnessed across Nigeria, as shown in previous studies by Adebayo (2015), Oladapo (2012), and others. Therefore, there is an urgent need for practical interventions that aligns architectural design with economic realities, and available technologies. Also, Institutions should add energy-efficient design and climate-responsive principles in architectural curriculum and other professional development studies. Local seminars and workshops in the State can help seal awareness gaps among practicing architects, builders, and also clients. The State government should collaborate with federal government agencies, to enforce existing codes such as the NBEEC and bring in

incentives (e.g., subsidies or tax relief) for buildings that use energy-saving features like insulation or solar panels. Publish and circulate design handbooks (simplified), for homeowners and developers that demonstrate the way low-cost passive strategies like window placement, tree planting, and overhang, can help in reducing energy usage without increasing construction costs. Launch government-supported pilot housing projects that showcase affordable, energy-efficient design in Imo's urban and semi-urban areas. Community engagement strategies, media, others, should be deployed to create awareness in the area of sustainable architecture, most especially in rapidly growing residential areas. Imo State will definitely move towards a better sustainable built environment if these recommendations are implemented. It will also reduce the cost of energy and improve indoor comfort while giving support to Nigeria's wider environmental goals.

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